

////////////////////////////////////

STRUCTURING DIVERGING IDEAS AND CONVERGING THEM TOWARD THE USER-AXIS: A DESIGN PROCESS

Mithra Zahedi, Giovanni De Paoli, Manon Guité
University of Montreal, Canada
mithra.zahedi@umontreal.ca

ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a model for human-computer interface design. Design activities are integrated into the early stages of the discovery process to bring stakeholders together and help them reach common goals and explore the project through collaboration. The model offers an environment for dealing with the complexity inherent to the design process when the aim is a human-centered design. The proposed model guides and structures the move around a central axis that represents the evolving users' interests by bringing all stakeholders to collaborate in design activities. Everyone's engagement around that central line, their dialogues and their exchange of information lead to the convergence of viewpoints and to enrichment of project knowledge for the team, more successful design, and development of the project in a timely and more economically efficient manner.

Keywords: User-centered design, HCI, model, interdisciplinary, project-grounded research.

INTRODUCTION

This paper discusses the problematic of design of human-computer interface (HCI) when a team composed by client, user, designer, and all other stakeholders collaborate. The paper proposes a model where design activities are staged to assist the team to achieve meaningful communications and align their focus on users' needs and wants. The ongoing development and increasing complexity of computer interfaces such as the Internet, or using a software program, impact not only our professional work, but also our social and economic interactions. HCI continually generates new opportunities and

problems which design has to address (Löwgren, & Stolterman, 2004). At the same time, unsuccessful design is generally accepted to be a direct result of an inadequate approach at the conceptual level, and in many cases, the inadequate approach is caused by miscommunication, misinterpretation, and lack of understanding among team members (Kleinsmann et al. 2007, Carrara et al. 2009). Being design practitioners and researchers, we presume that design activities have, in the early stages of design process, the potential to bring a diverse team together, help them focus on common goals, and achieve meaningful communication. This also means that the team should meet face-to-face and discuss diverse aspects of the project. As mentioned by Oak (2010), "face-to-face talk is an essential part of the collaborative practice of design, and occurs in tandem with the aforementioned modes of representation and communication (such as sketches and gestures)". In summery this paper outlines how design activities may be used as a method to help the team collaborate efficiently toward user-centeredness. We will discuss the problematic of the research, its methodological approach and the proposed model. We then present how the model was validated.

THE CONTEXT

Clearly a considerable amount of study about user-centered approach and usability has been undertaken in the field of HCI, and it is now well established that collaboration of a multidisciplinary team is crucial to develop user-centered interfaces (Boyarski, 1998; Carroll, 2000; Dourish, 2004; Löwgren & Stolterman, 2004; Preece et al, 2002). Already in 1998 Boyarski mentioned: "Without primary consideration for the people using the

artifacts we design, and the context for their use, – in short, the entire experience of use– we relegate design to a marginal and self-serving activity”. It is also well accepted that HCI design problems are complex and ill defined, and a disciplinary attitude alone can rarely succeed to solve them (Carroll, 2000; Dourish, 2004; Preece et al, 2002). A complex HCI design project cannot be decomposed into independent sub-elements; analysis of the problem and elaboration of the solution are not two consecutive steps, rather they are interconnected and progress in parallel (Löwgren, & Stolterman, 2004; Visser, 2006). As designers, we know that we are dealing with ‘messy’ situations and we understand the uniqueness of each project. However, when we deal with complex projects, it is essential that all stakeholders, with their diverging ideas, understand the messy nature of design problems and their uniqueness in order to increase the efficiency of user-centered design. In our experience however, we noticed that although all team members know that working with professionals in other disciplines is inevitable, they are not always prepared to perform in such a way to assure the needed collaboration from other disciplines. Team members do not share a common language of communication and common vision, do not hold a holistic perspective of the project, and do not have a similar understanding of the needs and motivations of the user (Carroll, 2000; Zahedi et al, 2010). In addition as explained by Kleinsmann diverse disciplines have their own operating procedures and ways in which they make representations of their ideas (Kleinsmann et al, 2007). In such context, how do we create the conditions for a variety of contributing experts and non-experts to go beyond their individual knowledge, thereby enriching their reflections in order to efficiently collaborate along a human-oriented design? Design is considered a social process (Nelson & Stolterman, 2003; Oak, 2010; Zahedi et al, 2010) that involves a project team to interact and negotiate. The team brings diverging ideas and interests that need to converge, especially in certain aspects, in order to permit optimal solutions for the project. One essential aspect is user-centeredness. We believe that some of HCI design activities (such as exploring the context, framing of problems and sketching) have the

capacity to be used as a method for modifying the dynamic of collaboration and creating conditions leading the multidisciplinary teams to user-centered interface solutions. In this regard there is a need to address the intertwined multidisciplinary situations where social, technological, political, or organizational problems are closely linked to design.

STUDY OF COLLABORATION

The following statement by Nigel Cross (although relating to the second generation of methods in the context of design methodology) encapsulates our point: “[...] process in which designers are partners with the problem owners” (2007). In HCI projects problem owners are clients, users, developers, content experts, project managers and so forth. In a collaborative approach, users as well as other stakeholders are invited to take part in the project, share their ideas and experiences with the design team. Theirs collective knowledge enables them to look at the project in a different way, to generate ideas and create new concepts (Carroll & Rosson, 2007). In this context, design process becomes a social negotiation among team members who need to communicate efficiently (Krippendorff, 2006). However, as Preece et al. (2002) state: “The more people there are with different backgrounds in a design team, the more difficult it can be to communicate and progress forward the designs being generated.” The reason seems to be that the lack of a common language among team members creates confusion and becomes the source of disinterest and dissatisfaction regarding the exchange of ideas. Also, team members don’t bring their knowledge to the team at the right time (Zahedi et al, 2010). All these problems make it difficult for them to consider the end user. As a result of these communication challenges, design process needs to deal with interactions and negotiations among people in addition to interactions between people and interfaces. Our research has focused on these communication challenges. It has been developed in the context of a professional design project in order to understand what really happens during the process of collaboration. Our goal as the designer/researcher was to understand what discussions and activities were fruitful for all problem owners; what motivated them to participate

fully and share their diverging ideas in a constructive way or what made them become passive; what approaches were acceptable by all and carried out successfully or unacceptable and abandoned; in meetings, what tools were helpful for demonstrating and understanding the complexity of the project. Project-grounded research (Findeli, 2004 and 2008, Jonas, 2006) was privileged for this study. This kind of research is about developing knowledge and theory related to design activity by going through an authentic design project. It conciliates theory and practice by situating theory in the project and by observing its implications on practice. In other words, “project” is the vehicle; conducting research and constructing knowledge become part of the design project. By engaging in project-grounded research, the professional design project became our field of study. Three successive and interconnected case studies informed our research. The case studies were about the design of different complex websites for a highly respected university institution. We focused on the dynamic of communication and collaboration between team members; documented each case study with descriptive field notes and analyzed and interpreted the notes using categories (Grounded theory, Glaser & Strauss, 1967). This was to establish theory from the study. The detailed explanation of the case studies is beyond the scope of this paper, however we will present briefly the two first ones and explain in more detail the last case where use of design activities as a method of communication and collaboration was a key aspect of the research project.

STUDY A

This case study focused on designer/researcher’s communication and interaction during the early phases of design (definition & analysis of the problem and visual concepts) within a conventional HCI design process. We examined how the designer collaborates with each involved discipline separately, collects information and creates a more comprehensive knowledge of the project for him/herself, and brings solutions through an iterative and cyclical design process. The main conclusions of this study are:

- Information is not fully given to the designer when it is needed;

- Stakeholders focus on their disciplinary domains, they don’t seek a holistic view of the project;
- There is a lack of common language;
- The project solution is crystallized through many back and forth conversations between the designer and other stakeholders.

STUDY B

This case study focused on collaborative interactions. A framework was created to study the conditions that could support collaboration between project team members (including designers, a manager and web developers) enabling them to have more constructive dialogue and exchanges of information, and to consider the user in all steps of their work. As a guiding principle, the designer/researcher facilitated the integration of the two first phases of design process in order to define the project’s goal and frame the problems, establish the information architecture, and create the guidelines of visual design. During multiple collaborative sessions, design activities were used as a method to foster consensus building and the adoption of a common language to develop mutual goals. The observations of this study showed that collaboration helped to:

- Generate a holistic vision and demonstrate the project’s complexity when the focus is on users need and wants;
- Facilitate communications and constructive exchanges between disciplines.

STUDY C

Limitations identified in these two cases and results from the use of design activities (that enhanced communication and collaboration) led to the design of an intervention that was implemented in the third case. The intervention comprised an intensive workshop of six full day at the beginning of the project whereby all stakeholders (client, content experts, office assistants, web programmers, users and designers) engaged in the design process. The team was encouraged to participate fully in discussions and express their viewpoints. A set of design activities (such as reflecting on the problematic, framing the problem, sketching, making mock-ups and so forth) structured the workshop. In

order to discover various aspects of the project, redefine goals, and reflect on diverse users' needs, the team started its collaboration by creating personas and use-scenarios. The activity became an informal learning process for all. New questions emerged and the team's interest in theory and its implications in practice grew. Throughout the activities many discussions took place that showed the diverging visions of the team and the controversies (it should be noted that while discussion is considered essential for collaboration in design, the attention here was on design activities and less focused on discussion). In our role of designer/mediator, we promoted the importance of focusing on users' changing and evolving needs. The will to build consensus led the team to dialogue and address the diverging issues, develop a common language and a shared understanding of the goals. It became clear, progressively, that the team got a more holistic vision of the project, which contributed to the change of perspective of each participant; the team focus converged towards users' interests. The availability of the stakeholders for a set period of time and their willingness to participate in the process through subsequent activities were the needed conditions for this intervention.

This brings to mind "Design thinking". Cross (2007) brought up Bruce Archer's belief that "there exists a designerly way of thinking and communicating that is both different from scientific and scholarly ways of thinking and communicating, and as powerful as scientific and scholarly methods of enquiry when applied to its own kinds of problems" (Bruce Archer, 1979 cited by Cross, 2007). Design thinking cannot be separated from the "designerly ways of knowing" (Cross, 2006) for which, we refer to Donald Schön (1983) and his view of "Reflective practitioner". He sought to establish "an epistemology of practice implicit in the artistic, intuitive processes which [design and other] practitioners bring to situations of uncertainty, instability, uniqueness and value conflict" (Cross, 2007). Design is a reflective practice and design thinking leads to formulating problems. Schön (1983) suggests that: "In order to formulate a design problem to be solved, the designer must frame a problematic design situation: set its boundaries, select particular things and relations for

attention, and impose on the situation a coherence that guides subsequent moves.

As the project evolved, the shared knowledge also evolved. Design activity helped the team understand how each one comprehends the project. Design activity was also a platform for negotiation, individually by trying different options, and collectively by discussing with others while they were working to create personas and later, the information architecture of the site. The experience of getting involved in design, brought the client, content experts, office assistants, users, designers, web developers, and managers, to achieve a common language and common goals. Their meaningful communication helped the team to construct new knowledge and offer optimal solutions for the project. The team defined project criteria, addressed the technology needs, and sketched the early version of the interface. Major findings from this study are:

- A particular way of collaboration between stakeholders is a key condition for leading a team to set the underlying principles of a user oriented and sustainable HCI design.
- Openness, sharing, trust, engagement and reflective practice characterize this collaboration.
- The intensive (uninterrupted) workshop where client, user, designer, and all other stakeholders collaborate offers the conditions for the convergence of perspectives and emergence of new ideas.
- All stakeholders should participate in design activities, mediated by designer. These activities improve the communication and knowledge construction.

Data generated from these three case studies informed the development of a theoretical model that represents steps of optimal collaborative HCI design process focusing on user-centeredness.

THE THEORETICAL DESIGN MODEL

The model supports and structures collaborative design activities of a multidisciplinary team with regards to designing user-centered interfaces. It is inevitably organized around a line that we call the

“User-Axis”. The function of this axis is to align communications, conversations, and individual or collective efforts of the team with the user. We use the term “user-axis” rather than “user-centered” to depict the idea of evolution and continuity regarding usability principles. Also, as the axis is a continuum, there is no target point; rather there is a direction to follow. Design process revolves around the user axis. The model is based on constructivism epistemology (Le Moigne, 1995). It is considered a tool that supports a project team during a HCI design process, when the goal is to achieve user-oriented results. The elements of the model are the following:

- Embracement of a “interdisciplinary attitude” by all project team members;
- Introduction of a “joint reflective practice”;
- Establishment of new phase called “extended discovery phase” at the beginning of the design process in which all team members participate actively in order to build consensus on the project goals and users’ needs/wants.

THE INTERDISCIPLINARY ATTITUDE

Each participating discipline in a HCI design project brings its visions, priorities, and motivations. However they need to make a significant move and align their interests rapidly with the user axis to achieve a common goal for the project. By embracing an interdisciplinary attitude the move becomes possible. Boyarski (1998) talks about an “interdisciplinary attitude” by which he means “integrating approaches from other disciplines, allowing ‘multiple sighting’ on a problem”. The interdisciplinary attitude brings shared commitment, acceptance of approaches from other disciplines, and a way of looking at the problem from various perspectives (Boyarski, 1998). It will allow openness to other perspectives and a willingness to share information. We consider the interdisciplinary attitude as a mind-set that encourages an informal teaching and learning dynamic. When all disciplinary knowledge is contextualized (for the project at hand), it will be easier for team members to understand diverse perspectives and see the relevance of diverging viewpoints (Senge, 1990).

Figure 1: Diverging foci (top) and converging toward user-axis (bottom).

To achieve good understanding as a team, each member needs to interact with others and become aware of all aspects and priorities presented by divers disciplines.

JOINT REFLECTIVE PRACTICE

As HCI design situations are complex and problems are interconnected, the design tasks require the confluence of a variety of expertise. When more people become involved in the design process, we also see more value conflicts. As mentioned earlier, Schön (1983) emphasizes the “complexity, uncertainty, instability, uniqueness, and the value conflicts” of situations of professional practice and explains that these situations are not problems to be solved. They are problematic situations, which are unclear, but they need to be understood. Reflective practice which considers design as an “action-oriented” activity (Schön, 1983), makes this understanding easier at an individual level. The theory behind this concept is that “designers are active in structuring the problem” (Schön, 1983) and they evaluate their actions in structuring and solving the problem. Designers have a “reflective conversation with the situation” (Schön, 1983). Introducing a joint reflective practice, where stakeholders are collaborating actively in structuring the problem, allows the team members to change their perspectives, bring together diverse knowledge and skills, notice interconnected problems, have a

dialogue with the problem and with each other, and challenge the concepts and theories by which it makes sense of knowledge. As a consequence of joint reflective practice, a project-specific team will bridge different understandings, formulate the project differently, and deal with uncertainty.

Figure 2: Alignment of disciplines and construction of new knowledge by joint reflective practice.

EXTENDED DISCOVERY PHASE

We illustrate (see Figure 3) the place of the intensive workshop in the process of HCI design and development. A phase called Extended discovery phase is created. During this phase, stakeholders redefine the project through consensus building. Their joint reflection on diverse aspects of the project crystallizes the design solution (phases 2 and 3, which relate to production, implementation and change management were not part of this study). During Extended discovery phase the team is brought together to collectively set the problem and establish the guiding principles of the project, which allow the development of the solution. Interdisciplinary attitude building and joint reflective practice play the role of foundations for this phase while design activities are used as a method for creating meaningful communications among the team members and help them converge toward the user axis. It is essential for the multidisciplinary team to consider the following four factors when they participate in the Extended discovery phase: the uniqueness of each project, the continuous change of user needs, the rapid development of information technology, and that HCI projects are generally complex and messy situations. We believe that to design with usability and sustainability in mind, the team needs to consider these factors and understand the relationship between them.

In a HCI design, there are three types of actions which need to happen one after the other during the Extended discovery phase: setting the problem, represented by ‘P layer’; outlining the information architecture, represented by ‘A layer’; and creating the visual design guidelines, represented by ‘V layer’. These actions are interwoven. The design process starts with the P layer and evolves around the user axis. Interdisciplinary attitude helps the team to create a common language and achieve consensus on project goals and priorities. The next step is tackling the A layer in order to define the structure of the project. Joint reflective practice supports the development of this layer. The final step is the V layer, which needs to take into account many elements that the project wants to communicate through the interface such as history, culture, and message. These layers interact which each other and with the user-axis and lead to a better understanding of the project and to the discovery of solutions. Dialogues that occur during the actions of these layers are of high importance to the effectiveness of the workshop and creativity of the participants.

Environment for joint reflective practice

Figure 3 illustrates an overview of the HCI design and development process as we see it. The illustration shows how the model became operational. The extended discovery phase consist of an environment that supports the workshop and technological tools.

Figure 3: An overview of the extended discovery phase of HCI design process

We call it Environment for joint reflective practice (EJRP). All stakeholders contribute to EJRP. The designer acts as designer/mediator at the beginning of the phase. This means that from design viewpoint, he/she has a neutral role during the workshop. Tools

such as wikis, project management software and job-aides are part of EJRP; they are used by contributors and facilitate collaboration and sharing of knowledge throughout the project.

VALIDATION

Having developed the model and tested some tools that facilitate its' operation, the next step of the research called for validation (Creswell, 2003; Deslauriers, 1991; Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Semi-structured interviews with three design experts were conducted. The experts had the following profiles: One was a researcher and an educator; and other was a senior design practitioner with many years of teaching experience; the third expert was a senior designer in HCI. Each interviewee answered two sets of questions. The first set was about the particular type of collaboration that was proposed: its need, its conditions, its value for HCI design projects, and so forth. The second set was focused on the model. The questions were formulated in order to determine if the model could: be operational in their practice, contribute in design of human-centered products and services, reduce the development time, be transferable in other design domains, and if they thought that designer should be the mediator of such workshops. The impact of the model in education was also discussed with two of the interviewees. Interview data collected from the conversations confirmed the validity of the concepts and activities depicted in the model as well as its transferability potential to other complex contexts. The model's limits were also discussed. Time management for this model can be demanding, as stakeholders need to make themselves available for a few consecutive days and concentrate on a single project, and particular knowledge is needed to facilitate the model's operation. It was also discussed that flexible tools could be developed for the model in order to make it easily operational. As a result of the positive response during this validation process, at this point no changes is made to the model.

CONCLUSION

Searching for effective ways of communication between disciplines has been a question for

researchers trying to find a new language that goes beyond the boundaries of individual disciplines. As a team, efficient communication and the sharing of knowledge between disciplines marks a move toward interdisciplinarity. According to Morin (1994), the interdisciplinary approach supports dialogue and the exchange of knowledge, analysis, and methods between two or more disciplines. It also implies interaction and a mutual enrichment between specialists (Boyarski 1998). This idea has been gaining acceptance by many researchers in HCI design. The intensive workshop supported by interdisciplinary attitude and joint reflective practice mirrored the theoretical model. We found that it is possible to encourage the design team in the early stage of the project, to approach the problem with a research stance, while keeping their focus on the end-users. When made operational, the workshop showed how communicating meaningfully through design helps collaboration. As discussed earlier, openness, sharing, trust, engagement and reflective practice, encourage this particular collaboration. The interplay of the scientific knowledge and design knowledge contributed to the understanding of the complexity of interface design. The workshop also significantly reduced the development time, and added value to the project by making the design more sustainable. This situation brings up the idea raised by Manzini (2008) that the transition toward sustainability is accomplished by "a radical change in ways of being and doing." As a result of our research, we believe that the designer needs to be trained for this new role that we call designer/mediator. Additional knowledge and a set of new skills will be required to enable the designer to organize and run the intensive workshop, facilitate the interactions among the team, facilitate the achievement of the needed attitude, keep the team focused on the goals, create a synergy and mediate the informal situation of learning and teaching. It is also to note that the back and forth between the design questions and research questions enriched both these activities.

REFERENCES

- Boyarski, D. (1998). Designing Design Education. *SIGCHI*, 30(3), 7-10.
- Boyarski, D., & Buchanan, R. (2000). Brief - Carnegie Mellon University. *Interactions*, March, April, 20-23.

- Carrara, G., Fioravanti, A., & Nanni, U. (2009). *An innovative knowledge structure for supporting collaboration in building design*. Paper presented at the Innovations for building and construction - Europa 12, Paris.
- Carroll, J. M. (2000). *Making use: scenario-based design of human-computer interactions*. Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press.
- Carroll, J., & Rosson, M. B. (2007). Participatory design in community informatics. *Design Studies*, 28(3), 243-261.
- Creswell, J. W. (2003). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. London: Sages Publications.
- Cross, N. (1993). Science and Design Methodology: A Review *Research in Engineering Design* (pp. 63-69). London: Springer-Verlag.
- Cross, N. (2001). Designerly Ways of Knowing: Design Discipline Versus Design Science. *Design Issues*, 17(3), 49-55.
- Cross, N. (2006). *Designerly Ways of Knowing*. London: Springer.
- Cross, N. (2007). Forty years of design research. *Design studies*, 28(1), 1-4.
- Deslauriers, J.-P. (1991). *Recherche qualitative - Guide pratique*. Montréal: Chenelière/McGraw-Hill.
- Dourish, P. (2004). *Where the action is: the foundations of embodied interaction*. Cambridge: The MIT Press.
- Findeli, A. (1998). La recherche en design, questions épistémologiques et méthodologiques. *International Journal of Design and Innovation Research*, 1(1).
- Findeli, A. (2004, 13-14 mai). *La recherche-projet : une méthode pour la recherche en design*. Paper presented at the Symposium de recherche sur le design, Tenu à la HGK de Bâle sous les auspices du Swiss Design Network
- Findeli, A. (2008). *Research Through Design and Transdisciplinarity: A Tentative Contribution to the Methodology of Design Research*. Paper presented at the Swiss design Network Symposium 2008.
- Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. L. (1967). *The discovery of Grounded Theory: Strategies for Qualitative Research*. Chicago: Aldine.
- Jonas, W. (2007). Design Research and its Meaning to the Methodological Development of the Discipline. In R. Michel (Ed.), *Design Research Now: Essays and Selected Projects* (pp. 187-206). Basel, Boston, Berlin: Birkhäuser Verlag AG.
- Kleinsmann, M., Valkenburg, R., & Buijs, J. (2007). Why do(n't) actors in collaborative design understand each others? An empirical study towards a better understanding of collaborative design. *CoDesign*, 3(59-73).
- Krippendorff, K. (2006). *The semantic turn: a new foundation for design*. Boca Raton, Florida: CRC Taylor & Francis Group.
- Le Moigne, J.-L. (1999). *Les épistémologies constructivistes*. Dunod
- Linard, M. (2001). Concevoir des environnements pour apprendre : l'activité humaine, cadre organisateur de l'interactivité technique. *Sciences et techniques éducatives*, 8(3-4), 211-238.
- Lincoln, Y., & Guba, E. (1985). *Naturalistic Inquiry*. USA: Sage.
- Löwgren, J., & Stolterman, E. (2004). *Thoughtful Interaction Design: A Design Perspective on Information Technology*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: MIT Press.
- Manzini, E. (2008). Viewpoint. New design knowledge. *Design studies*, 30, 4-12.
- Morin, E. (1994). EDGAR MORIN, Sur l'interdisciplinarité. *Bulletin Interactif du Centre International de Recherches et Études transdisciplinaires n° 2, juin*.
- Nelson, H. G., & Stolterman, E. (2003). *The design way*. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Educational Technology Publications.
- Oak, A. (2010). What can talk tell us about design?: Analyzing conversation to understand practice. *Design Studies*, 32(3), 211-234.
- Preece, J., Rogers, Y., & Sharp, H. (2002). *Interaction Design: beyond human-computer interaction*. New York.
- Rittel, H., & Webber, M. (1973). *Dilemmas in General Theory of Planning*, PP 155-169. Paper presented at the Working Papers from the Urban & Regional Development.
- Schön, D. A. (1983). *The Reflective Practitioner: How Professionals Think in Action*. New York: Basic books.
- Senge, P. (1990). *The fifth discipline: The art and practice of the learning organization*. New York: Currency Doubleday
- Suchman, L. A. (2007). *Human-Machine Reconfigurations: Plans and Situated Actions*, 2nd Edition: Cambridge University Press.
- Visser, W. (2006). *The cognitive artifacts of designing*. Mahwah, New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Zahedi, M., Guité, M., & De Paoli, G. (2010, July 7-9). *Dealing with the human-centered approach within HCI projects* Paper presented at the Design Research Society (DRS) international conference Design & Complexity, Montréal.
- Zimmerman, J., Forlizzi, J., & Evenson, S. (2007, April 28-May 3, 2007). *Research Through design as a Method for Design in HCI*. Paper presented at the CHI 2007, San Jose, California.